

29 April 2026, Groningen, Netherlands

Members of the society are respectfully invited to attend the Annual General Meeting of the Society, to be held at 09:00 Central European Standard Time, on the 13th day of May, 2026, in the Hotel Zuiderduin (Lamoraalzaal), Egmond aan Zee, the Netherlands.

The meeting is held in conjunction with the 81st Netherlands Astronomy Conference, all members are invited to attend regardless of registration for the conference as a whole. To ensure access to the venue, please contact the secretary if you plan to attend without meeting registration at least one hour in advance of the meeting.

Please submit apologies for absence; proposed business items; or, in case you will not be present, comments, opinion, or votes on agenda items, or other matters, to be included in the record; to the secretary at least 24 hours before the announced meeting time.

Relevant documents will be provided to members at least 48 hours prior to the meeting, or during the meeting, as appropriate.

Agenda *(as proposed)*

Annual General Meeting 13 May 2026, 09:00 CEST

1. Opening of the meeting
2. Adoption of the Agenda
3. Board Announcements
 - a. Board Membership and approval of new board members
 - b. Board Meetings

- c. Other Announcements of the Board
- 4. Approval of Minutes
 - a. AGM 2025 (27 May 2025, Berg en Dal, Netherlands)
- 5. 2025 Annual Report of the Secretary
 - a. Secretary's Report
 - i. Report and membership data
 - ii. Report from the EAS
 - iii. Report from (or on behalf of) the Archives
 - iv. Process for termination of membership
 - b. Executive Office Report
 - i. Report on servers, apps, and other services
- 6. 2025 Treasury Reports and Actions
 - a. Financial Statement 2025
 - i. Treasurer's report
 - ii. Report of the Financial Audit Committee
 - b. RNAS Grants and Awards Policies and Plans
 - i. Motion for spending on Grants and Awards, per the membership, board, or executive committee
 - c. Proposed Budget 2026 and 2027
 - i. Motion of change in budget cycle to approve new annual budgets in the prior year (thus 2027 budget here), subject to mid-budget amendment in the current year.
 - d. Election of the 2026 Financial Audit Committee

7. 2025 Annual Report of the Chair
8. Any Other Business (Rondvraag)
9. Announcements
10. Closing of the Meeting

Respectfully submitted / Hoogachtend,,

Dr. J. Noel-Storr, Secretary/Secretaris
secretary@kna-rnas.nl

On behalf of the board.